

SUPPORTING DATA FOR THE FOLLOWING PAPER PUBLISHED
IN THE JOURNAL OF DAIRY SCIENCE

Mammary gland responses to altering the supply of de novo fatty acid substrates and preformed fatty acids on the yields of milk components and fatty acids

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INTERPRETIVE SUMMARY

Mammary gland responses to altering the supply of de novo fatty acid substrates and preformed fatty acids on the yields of milk components and fatty acids. *By Benoit et al.* The objective of our study was to evaluate the effect of altering the supply of acetate, palmitic acid (PA), and cottonseed on the yields of milk components and fatty acids (FA) in lactating dairy cows. Three-way interactions among acetate, PA, and cottonseed were observed for the yields of milk fat, 3.5% fat-corrected milk (FCM) and the molar yields of de novo FA, mixed FA, and preformed FA. Basal diets supplemented with PA increased mixed FA yield. Diets containing acetate increased the yields of milk fat, de novo FA, mixed FA, and preformed FA compared to diets without acetate. Diets containing cottonseed increased the yields of milk and preformed FA but decreased the yields of de novo and mixed FA compared to diets without cottonseed. The observed three-way interactions emphasize the importance of balancing the supply of de novo FA substrates and preformed FA to the mammary gland for increased milk FA synthesis.

Supplemental Table S1. Milk production responses for cows fed treatment diets.

Item	Basal diets ¹ and Treatments ²								SEM	<i>P</i> -value ³ Basal diet × Acetate × Cottonseed	
	Low PA				High PA						
	CON	AC	CS	CS+AC	CON	AC	CS	CS+AC			
Yield, kg/d											
Milk	48.6	48.2	48.9	49.7	46.8	46.6	47.4	48.0	1.84	0.75	
ECM	49.8	52.2	49.5	52.4	50.6	51.1	50.4	53.2	1.74	0.14	
FCM	49.1 ^b	51.8 ^a	49.5 ^b	52.3 ^a	50.9 ^b	51.8 ^b	50.5 ^b	54.0 ^a	1.78	0.08	
Fat	1.73 ^b	1.91 ^a	1.77 ^b	1.90 ^a	1.89 ^c	1.96 ^b	1.83 ^c	2.04 ^a	0.07	<0.01	
Protein	1.57	1.56	1.56	1.61	1.50	1.48	1.51	1.51	0.05	0.32	
Lactose	2.39	2.35	2.40	2.44	2.29	2.30	2.32	2.37	0.10	0.66	
Component, %											
Fat	3.56 ^c	3.99 ^a	3.62 ^c	3.83 ^b	4.09 ^b	4.26 ^a	4.05 ^b	4.26 ^a	0.11	0.04	
Protein	3.24	3.26	3.21	3.22	3.24	3.21	3.23	3.20	0.06	0.59	
Lactose	4.87	4.90	4.88	4.90	4.90	4.94	4.90	4.94	0.03	0.35	
MUN, mg/dL	11.3	10.6	11.3	10.5	12.1	11.3	12.2	11.8	0.27	0.12	
Milk/DMI	1.53	1.46	1.60	1.58	1.44	1.46	1.57	1.57	0.05	0.28	
ECM/DMI	1.53	1.54	1.64	1.66	1.55	1.59	1.67	1.74	0.04	0.82	
FCM/DMI	1.51	1.55	1.63	1.65	1.57	1.61	1.67	1.77	0.04	0.25	
BW, kg	727	729	723	729	742	738	740	740	16.0	0.94	
BW change ⁶	9.71	10.2	7.51	8.50	15.1	5.95	10.5	5.49	3.2	0.68	
BCS	3.01	2.98	3.00	3.02	3.13	3.13	3.10	3.14	0.07	0.87	
BCS change ⁶	0.03	-0.07	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.26	
Insulin, μ IU/mL	11.7	10.6	10.4	11.3	13.3	12.2	11.3	11.1	0.68	0.37	

^{a-d}Means in a row within each basal diet (Low PA and High PA) with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

¹Low PA = basal diet with no supplemental FA and High PA = basal diet with a FA supplement containing 85% palmitic acid (PA).

²CON = the control diet, AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate, CS = the control diet containing 12% whole cottonseed, and CS+AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate and 12% whole cottonseed.

³Refers to results from ANOVA for the interaction among basal diet, acetate, and cottonseed.

Supplemental Table S2. Summation by source and individual fatty acid (FA) molar yields (mmol/d) of milk for cows fed treatment diets

Item	Basal diets ¹ and Treatments ²								SEM	<i>P</i> -value ³ Basal diet × Acetate × Cottonseed
	Low PA				High PA					
	CON	AC	CS	CS+AC	CON	AC	CS	CS+AC		
Source, mmol/d										
De novo	2610 ^b	2800 ^a	2410 ^c	2610 ^b	2710 ^a	2770 ^a	2370 ^b	2660 ^a	106	0.06
Mixed	2390 ^c	2730 ^a	2250 ^d	2570 ^b	2900 ^b	3110 ^a	2640 ^c	3060 ^a	114	0.04
Preformed	1960 ^b	2050 ^b	2370 ^a	2380 ^a	2010 ^c	2040 ^c	2260 ^b	2400 ^a	79.1	0.05
FA, mmol/d										
C4:0	506 ^b	585 ^a	529 ^b	580 ^a	588 ^b	645 ^a	565 ^b	659 ^a	25.8	0.04
C6:0	280 ^c	320 ^a	277 ^c	299 ^b	313 ^b	329 ^a	278 ^c	322 ^{ab}	13.2	<0.01
C8:0	143 ^b	158 ^a	136 ^c	143 ^b	152 ^{ab}	155 ^a	132 ^c	147 ^b	6.60	<0.01
C10:0	339	346	295	311	332	325	278	302	15.3	0.19
C12:0	354	361	297	312	342	337	279	297	16.2	0.37
C14:0	909	961	838	907	885	905	784	877	36.5	0.12
<i>cis</i> -9 C14:1	77.1	76.0	60.8	62.4	71.2	70.3	53.4	55.8	4.29	0.85
C16:0	2270 ^c	2600 ^a	2180 ^c	2460 ^b	2770 ^b	2930 ^a	2560 ^c	2940 ^a	107	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	121 ^a	125 ^a	105 ^b	107 ^b	134 ^a	133 ^a	108 ^c	115 ^b	6.90	0.03
C18:0	439 ^c	510 ^b	637 ^a	658 ^a	480 ^d	522 ^c	637 ^b	718 ^a	28.4	0.03
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	10.6	11.3	15.7	15.7	11.1	11.1	13.8	14.0	0.56	0.29
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	28.6	23.1	33.9	30.3	24.0	20.5	27.6	24.7	2.5	0.52
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	41.5	52.3	63.3	65.0	41.2	45.4	50.7	53.7	3.5	0.16
<i>trans</i> -12 C18:1	22.2	22.6	35.5	34.0	20.4	20.2	28.4	27.8	1.42	0.34
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	884	896	1030	1040	942	951	1000	1060	38.2	0.27
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	46.2	46.7	49.0	49.1	41.0	38.6	43.7	44.6	2.31	0.21
<i>cis</i> -12 C18:1	31.2	30.9	46.8	44.5	28.6	27.9	37.5	36.0	2.20	0.66
<i>cis</i> -13 C18:1	5.26	5.26	6.22	5.80	5.07	4.94	5.44	5.35	0.33	0.19
<i>cis</i> -9,12 C18:2	168	173	163	166	172	170	160	165	5.85	0.27
<i>cis</i> -9,12,15 C18:3	18.5	18.1	15.6	15.4	17.7	17.1	14.1	15.0	0.60	0.15

^{a-d}Means in a row within each basal diet (Low PA and High PA) with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

¹Low PA = basal diet with no supplemental FA and High PA = basal diet with a FA supplement containing 85% palmitic acid (PA).

²CON = the control diet, AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate, CS = the control diet containing 12% whole cottonseed, and CS+AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate and 12% whole cottonseed.

³Refers to results from ANOVA for the interaction among basal diet, acetate, and cottonseed.

Supplemental Table S3. Summation by source and individual fatty acid (FA) mass yields (g/d) of milk for cows fed treatment diets.

Item	Treatment ¹				SEM	Basal diet ²			P-value ³						
	CON	AC	CS	CS+AC		Low PA	High PA	SEM	Basal diet	Acetate ⁴	Cottonseed ⁵	Acetate × Cottonseed	Basal diet × Acetate	Basal diet × Cottonseed	Basal diet × Acetate × Cottonseed
Source, g/d ⁶															
De novo	455 ^b	471 ^a	405 ^c	443 ^b	13.1	447	440	17.6	0.76	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.73	0.46	0.06
Mixed	678 ^c	743 ^a	635 ^d	721 ^b	20.3	639	749	27.6	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.10	0.47	0.73	<0.01
Preformed	565	577	667	682	15.4	623	623	20.4	0.99	0.03	<0.01	0.85	0.53	0.03	0.30
FA, g/d															
C4:0	48.2	54.6	48.2	54.6	1.61	48.7	54.1	2.10	0.08	<0.01	0.99	0.96	0.69	0.62	0.01
C6:0	34.5	37.7	32.3	36.0	1.08	34.2	36.1	1.43	0.35	<0.01	<0.01	0.52	0.81	0.26	<0.01
C8:0	21.5	22.6	19.3	20.9	0.67	20.9	21.2	0.88	0.77	<0.01	<0.01	0.33	0.92	0.19	0.04
C10:0	57.4 ^a	58.2 ^a	49.4 ^c	52.7 ^b	1.90	55.6	53.2	2.53	0.51	<0.01	<0.01	0.09	0.37	0.84	0.07
C12:0	69.7 ^a	69.9 ^a	57.7 ^c	61.0 ^b	2.29	66.3	62.8	3.03	0.42	0.06	<0.01	0.08	0.64	0.85	0.37
C14:0	205 ^b	213 ^a	185 ^c	204 ^b	5.89	206	197	7.94	0.41	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.82	0.92	0.12
<i>cis</i> -9 C14:1	16.8 ^a	16.6 ^a	12.9 ^b	13.4 ^b	0.69	15.6	14.2	0.94	0.28	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	0.76	0.48	0.85
C16:0	646 ^b	710 ^a	608 ^c	692 ^a	19.3	610	718	26.2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.10	0.49	0.70	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	32.4	33.1	27.0	28.2	1.25	29.2	31.3	1.71	0.44	<0.01	<0.01	0.51	0.86	0.13	0.02
C18:0	131	147	181	196	5.70	160	168	7.25	0.44	<0.01	<0.01	0.79	0.43	0.86	0.03
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	3.06	3.16	4.17	4.19	0.11	3.77	3.53	0.15	0.25	0.23	<0.01	0.38	0.58	<0.01	0.29
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	7.44 ^b	5.95 ^c	8.52 ^a	7.62 ^b	0.48	8.17	6.59	0.64	0.09	<0.01	<0.01	0.10	0.58	0.03	0.99
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	11.7 ^c	13.8 ^b	16.1 ^a	16.8 ^a	0.69	15.7	13.5	0.85	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	0.34	<0.01	0.16
<i>trans</i> -12 C18:1	6.02	6.04	9.02	8.73	0.28	8.07	6.83	0.38	0.03	0.21	<0.01	0.15	0.88	<0.01	0.34
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	258	261	287	296	7.51	272	279	9.72	0.59	0.07	<0.01	0.34	0.32	0.02	0.27
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	12.3	12.0	13.1	13.2	0.46	13.5	11.8	0.59	0.06	0.77	<0.01	0.35	0.51	0.25	0.21
<i>cis</i> -12 C18:1	8.45	8.30	11.9	11.4	0.44	10.8	9.18	0.57	0.05	0.09	<0.01	0.33	0.87	<0.01	0.66
<i>cis</i> -13 C18:1	1.46	1.44	1.65	1.58	0.06	1.59	1.47	0.09	0.32	0.07	<0.01	0.28	0.56	0.04	0.19
<i>cis</i> -9,12 C18:2	47.6	48.1	45.3	46.4	1.15	46.9	46.8	1.49	0.93	0.16	<0.01	0.55	0.47	0.58	0.27
<i>cis</i> -9,12,15 C18:3	5.03 ^a	4.88 ^a	4.10 ^b	4.23 ^b	0.12	4.70	4.41	0.15	0.17	0.87	<0.01	0.01	0.34	0.83	0.04

^{a-d}Means in a row with different superscripts differ. Shown only if observed an interaction between acetate and cottonseed ($P < 0.05$).

¹CON = the control diet, AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate, CS = the control diet containing 12% whole cottonseed, and CS+AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate and 12% whole cottonseed.

²Low PA = diet with no supplemental FA and High PA = diet with a FA supplement containing 85% palmitic acid (PA).

³P-values refer to results from ANOVA for main effects of basal diet, acetate, and cottonseed and their interactions.

⁴Acetate = diets containing 3% sodium acetate compared to diets with no sodium acetate.

⁵Cottonseed = diets containing 12% whole cottonseed compared to diets with no whole cottonseed.

⁶FA sources determined as de novo < 16 carbons, mixed = 16-carbon, and preformed > 16 carbons.

Supplemental Table S4. Summation by source and individual fatty acid (FA) mass yields (g/d) of milk for cows fed treatment diets

Item	Treatments ^{1,2}								SEM	<i>P</i> -value ³ Basal diet × Acetate × Cottonseed
	Low PA				High PA					
	CON	AC	CS	CS+AC	CON	AC	CS	CS+AC		
Source, g/d										
De novo	452 ^b	478 ^a	414 ^c	444 ^b	458 ^a	464 ^a	396 ^b	441 ^a	18.5	0.06
Mixed	613 ^c	700 ^a	586 ^d	658 ^b	743 ^b	785 ^a	684 ^c	783 ^a	28.9	<0.01
Preformed	557	572	679	683	573	583	655	680	22.1	0.30
FA, g/d										
C4:0	44.6 ^b	52.5 ^a	46.6 ^b	51.1 ^a	51.8 ^b	56.8 ^a	49.8 ^b	58.1 ^a	2.29	0.01
C6:0	32.6 ^c	37.2 ^a	32.2 ^c	34.7 ^b	36.4 ^b	38.2 ^a	32.3 ^c	37.3 ^{ab}	1.54	<0.01
C8:0	20.9 ^b	22.5 ^a	19.6 ^c	20.6 ^{bc}	22.2 ^{ab}	22.6 ^a	19.0 ^c	21.1 ^b	0.95	0.04
C10:0	57.7 ^b	60.5 ^a	50.9 ^c	53.5 ^b	57.1 ^a	56.0 ^a	47.9 ^c	51.9 ^b	2.69	0.07
C12:0	71.0	72.3	59.5	62.4	68.5	67.5	55.8	59.5	3.24	0.37
C14:0	208	219	191	207	202	207	179	200	8.33	0.12
<i>cis</i> -9 C14:1	17.5	17.2	13.8	14.1	16.1	15.9	12.1	12.6	0.97	0.85
C16:0	582 ^c	668 ^a	559 ^c	630 ^b	709 ^b	751 ^a	656 ^c	754 ^a	27.5	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	30.7 ^b	32.3 ^a	26.7 ^c	27.1 ^c	34.0 ^a	33.8 ^a	27.4 ^c	29.2 ^b	1.77	0.02
C18:0	125 ^c	145 ^b	181 ^a	187 ^a	137 ^d	148 ^c	181 ^b	204 ^a	8.07	0.03
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	3.00	3.18	4.44	4.44	3.12	3.14	3.90	3.94	0.16	0.29
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	8.09	6.50	9.55	8.55	6.79	5.40	7.49	6.69	0.68	0.99
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	11.7	14.8	17.9	18.4	11.6	12.8	14.3	15.2	0.97	0.16
<i>trans</i> -12 C18:1	6.28	6.39	10.0	9.60	5.76	5.69	8.02	7.85	0.40	0.34
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	250	253	291	293	266	269	283	299	10.8	0.27
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	13.0	13.2	13.8	13.9	11.6	10.9	12.3	12.6	0.65	0.21
<i>cis</i> -12 C18:1	8.81	8.72	13.2	12.6	8.08	7.80	10.6	10.2	0.62	0.66
<i>cis</i> -13 C18:1	1.48	1.48	1.76	1.64	1.43	1.40	1.54	1.51	0.09	0.19
<i>cis</i> -9,12 C18:2	47.1	48.5	45.7	46.5	48.2	47.7	45.0	46.2	1.64	0.27
<i>cis</i> -9,12,15 C18:3	5.14 ^a	5.05 ^a	4.34 ^b	4.29 ^b	4.92 ^a	4.70 ^a	3.86 ^c	4.17 ^b	0.17	0.04

^{a-d}Means in a row within each basal diet (Low PA and High PA) with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

¹Low PA = basal diet with no supplemental FA and High PA = basal diet with a FA supplement containing 85% palmitic acid (PA).

²CON = the control diet, AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate, CS = the control diet containing 12% whole cottonseed, and CS+AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate and 12% whole cottonseed.

³Refers to results from ANOVA for the interaction among basal diet, acetate, and cottonseed.

Supplemental Table S5. Summation by source and individual fatty acid (FA) concentration of milk for cows fed treatment diets.

Item	Treatment ¹				SEM	Basal diet ²			P-value ³							
	CON	AC	CS	CS+AC		Low PA	High PA	SEM	Basal diet	Acetate ⁴	Cottonseed ⁵	Acetate × Cottonseed	Basal diet × Acetate	Basal diet × Cottonseed	Basal diet × Acetate × Cottonseed	
Source, g/100g FA ⁶																
De novo	26.7	26.2	24.0	23.9	0.29	26.1	24.3	0.36	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.16	0.21	0.35	0.77	
Mixed	39.6	41.2	36.9	38.8	0.34	36.9	41.4	0.43	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.35	0.41	0.91	0.75	
Preformed	33.4 ^c	32.7 ^d	39.1 ^a	37.2 ^b	0.36	36.9	34.3	0.40	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.88	0.41	0.37	
FA, g/100g FA																
C4:0	2.82 ^c	3.00 ^a	2.83 ^c	2.94 ^b	0.04	2.84	2.95	0.04	0.09	<0.01	0.22	0.08	0.28	0.25	0.43	
C6:0	2.01	2.08	1.89	1.94	0.02	1.99	1.97	0.03	0.57	<0.01	<0.01	0.50	0.45	0.11	0.24	
C8:0	1.26	1.25	1.14	1.13	0.02	1.22	1.17	0.02	0.07	0.28	<0.01	0.99	0.66	0.66	0.25	
C10:0	3.39	3.23	2.94	2.84	0.06	3.23	2.96	0.08	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.19	0.63	0.30	0.62	
C12:0	4.12 ^a	3.84 ^b	3.41 ^c	3.28 ^d	0.08	3.84	3.48	0.11	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.05	0.71	0.07	0.60	
C14:0	12.1 ^a	11.9 ^b	11.0 ^c	11.0 ^c	0.14	12.0	10.9	0.17	<0.01	0.13	<0.01	0.07	0.16	0.17	0.41	
<i>cis</i> -9 C14:1	1.00 ^a	0.91 ^b	0.77 ^c	0.73 ^d	0.03	0.91	0.79	0.05	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	0.05	0.29	0.54	0.24	
C16:0	37.8	39.3	35.4	37.4	0.32	35.3	39.7	0.40	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.18	0.33	0.74	0.42	
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	1.89	1.82	1.57	1.52	0.05	1.69	1.71	0.06	0.77	<0.01	<0.01	0.39	0.22	0.90	0.58	
C18:0	7.71 ^c	8.19 ^b	10.7 ^a	10.6 ^a	0.20	9.37	9.24	0.24	0.70	0.11	<0.01	0.04	0.64	0.65	0.48	
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	0.18 ^c	0.17 ^d	0.25 ^a	0.23 ^b	0.004	0.22	0.20	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.08	0.94	<0.01	0.88	
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	0.43	0.33	0.50	0.42	0.03	0.48	0.36	0.04	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.61	0.23	0.10	0.89	
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	0.69 ^c	0.76 ^b	0.96 ^a	0.91 ^a	0.04	0.92	0.75	0.04	0.01	0.52	<0.01	0.01	0.42	<0.01	0.35	
<i>trans</i> -12 C18:1	0.36	0.34	0.51	0.48	0.01	0.46	0.38	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.15	0.98	<0.01	0.14	
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	15.2	14.5	17.0	16.2	0.21	16.0	15.5	0.24	0.14	<0.01	<0.01	0.75	0.44	0.12	0.76	
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	0.73	0.67	0.78	0.72	0.02	0.80	0.65	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.96	0.59	0.06	0.74	
<i>cis</i> -12 C18:1	0.50 ^c	0.46 ^d	0.70 ^a	0.62 ^b	0.02	0.63	0.51	0.03	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	0.34	<0.01	0.47	
<i>cis</i> -13 C18:1	0.09 ^b	0.08 ^c	0.10 ^a	0.09 ^b	0.003	0.09	0.08	0.003	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	0.17	0.12	0.82	
<i>cis</i> -9,12 C18:2	2.77	2.64	2.68	2.53	0.05	2.74	2.58	0.06	0.09	<0.01	<0.01	0.51	0.85	0.10	0.82	
<i>cis</i> -9,12,15 C18:3	0.30	0.27	0.24	0.23	0.004	0.27	0.25	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.14	0.26	

^{a-d}Means in a row with different superscripts differ. Shown only if observed an interaction between acetate and cottonseed ($P < 0.05$).

¹CON = the control diet, AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate, CS = the control diet containing 12% whole cottonseed, and CS+AC = the control diet containing 3% sodium acetate and 12% whole cottonseed.

²Low PA = diet with no supplemental FA and High PA = diet with a FA supplement containing 85% palmitic acid (PA).

³P-values refer to results from ANOVA for main effects of basal diet, acetate, and cottonseed and their interactions.

⁴Acetate = diets containing 3% sodium acetate compared to diets with no sodium acetate.

⁵Cottonseed = diets containing 12% whole cottonseed compared to diets with no whole cottonseed.

⁶FA sources determined as de novo < 16 carbons, mixed = 16-carbon, and preformed > 16 carbons.